

resorcinol which might be the reason for lower rate and small decrease in entropy of activation. This is a well known fact that oxalic acid and malonic acid associate through hydrogen bonding to some extent, past the dimer stage to form "Supermolecules" composed of three to four single molecules each⁶. It can be assumed that the single molecule of oxamic acid is responsible for the formation of the transition complex whereas for the dicarboxylic acids associated and molecules may be involved. The intermediate complex may be in the form (Fig. 1).

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzyl Alcohol by Peroxydisulphate Ion

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THE kinetics of oxidation of different alcohols by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ has been studied by previous workers^{1,2}. In the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by $S_2O_8^{2-}$, Bacon and Doggart³ have shown the formation of benzaldehyde, benzoic acid and a resinous product, but the kinetics of this reaction has not been studied so far. A kinetic study of this reaction is presented in this paper.

Experimental

The experimental set up was similar to that adopted in the reaction of phthalic acid and peroxydisulphate ion⁴.

The preliminary experiments have shown that the uncatalysed reaction is very slow, however, Ag^+ catalysed reaction proceeds with measurable velocity at 30° and above.

Results

Stoichiometry: It is found that one mole of $K_2S_2O_8$ reacts with one mole of Benzyl alcohol upto the formation of benzaldehyde, according to the equation

The overall reaction was found to obey first order behaviour at different $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$. However, the first order specific rate was found to decrease with the increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ at constant μ and constant $[K^+]$. This may be due to trace impurities present in Analar grade of $K_2S_2O_8$.

However, on recrystallising the sample of Analar $K_2S_2O_8$ three times, the rate constant was found to slightly increase with the increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ which tends to confirm that trace impurities are probably responsible for this behaviour.

It is pertinent to point out that similar behaviour has been observed in α -phenyl ethanol oxidation⁵.

The reaction is first order in $K_2S_2O_8$ and $AgNO_3$ and Zero order in Benzyl alcohol. Further the first order rate constant remains unaffected by changing $[Benzyl\ alcohol]$.

From a study at six different temperatures (from 308 to 328° K) the following energy parameters were obtained.

$$E = 18.05 \text{ K. Cal. mole}^{-1}, A = 5.57 \times 10^8 \text{ sec.}^{-1} \\ \text{and } \Delta S^\ddagger = -20.61 \text{ E.U.}$$

A large negative value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ suggests that the formation of activated complex involves a reaction either between two oppositely charged ions or between an ion and a neutral molecule. The value of E is approximately of the same order as for the oxidation of 2-propanol⁶ in presence of dissolved oxygen. A large value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ has been reported for a number of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of peroxydisulphate ion⁴⁻⁶.

The effect of ionic strength is of the same type as found in the oxidation of other alcohols⁷. The negative salt effect suggest that the rate determining process may be between two oppositely charged ions. Similarly the specific inhibitory effect of different ions is also in the same order

In the same manner allyl acetate greatly inhibits the reaction which is suggestive of radical mechanism.

Analysis of the products at different times shows that the amount of benzaldehyde found passes through a maximum while the amount of benzoic acid goes on steadily increasing with time. This leads us to conclude that it is a case of consecutive reaction leading

first to the formation of benzaldehyde and then the oxidation of benzaldehyde to give benzoic acid. It is observed that the amount of benzoic acid starts decreasing slightly after 180 min which can be attributed to its further slow oxidation and polymerisation to give resin⁹.

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Some New Initiators (Simple and Redox) for Polymerization

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THE possibility of initiation with halogen-source materials was visualized during the study of such with halogens^{1,2}. Some new initiator systems (most of them containing halogen or halogen-source material as one component) are depicted herein.

The polymerization was carried out in the dark by wrapping the vessels with black paper. Photopolymerization was done in pyrex sealing tubes with PCl_5 and $SOCl_2$ in anhydrous media. Yield by PCl_5 and $SOCl_2$ containing systems was always corrected with a blank. $SOCl_2$ was added from micro-pipette and the concentration of PCl_5 was measured by hydrolysis followed by acidimetric titrations. H_2S bubbled through N_2 -flushed water and aqueous I_2 -water were used. H_2S concentration was determined by precipitation with excess $CuSO_4$ solution followed by iodometric titrations.

PCl_5 and $SOCl_2$: From Table 1 it follows that PCl_5 acts as a photoinitiator whereas $SOCl_2$ does not do so. As shown by end group analysis chlorine atoms are produced from PCl_5 or its complex with benzene. In contrast with PCl_5 a good thermal initiating system is formed with $SOCl_2$, evidently due to formation of chlorine radicals by thermal decomposition at as low a temperature as 70° , either in bulk or in solution in a typical solvent viz. petroleum ether. In the latter case the chlorine radicals first formed may attack the hydrocarbon and produce active hydrocarbon radical. There is a basic difference in PCl_5 and $SOCl_2$ systems since in the former case, except under U V., chlorine end group is absent. Moderate values (η) even in high concentration of the initiators are also a distinguishing feature of these systems.

A few other redox initiating systems: H_2S is the simplest thiol member and progress of polymerization using H_2S is hindered probably by high chain terminating action of SH radicals (Table 2). The failure of $KMnO_4$ -HCl system raises a question regarding the involvement of chlorine atoms as an intermediate in this reaction and its role as initiator. The formation of I_2 -redox in both aqueous and non-aqueous medium (Tables 2 and 3) is surprising in view of the normal inhibiting action of I_2 .

TABLE 1—POLYMERIZATION WITH HALOGEN-SOURCE MATERIAL

Halogen source material concentration	Second redox component concn.	Monomer (MMA) concn.	Condition of polymerization (time, temp. etc.)	Polymer yield %	$[\eta]$ in benzene at 30°	Polymer end group
PCl_5 , $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ (in benzene solution)	x	7.8 M	Wrapped in black paper and kept for 6 hours at 70°	nil	—	—
$SOCl_2$, 0.1 M	X	Bulk, 5 ml	At U.V. (40°) for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hr	10%	1.2	Chlorine
$SOCl_2$, 0.10 M	X	Bulk, 1 ml	At U.V. (40°) for 3 hr	nil	—	—
PCl_5 , 0.12 M (in $CHCl_3$ solution)	Benzyl Alcohol	4.7 M	At 70° for 4 hr	34.3%	1.8	Chlorine
	0.23 M		At 30° 24 hr	8%	0.5	—
PCl_5 , $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ (in benzene solution)	n-butyl amine, 0.34 M	8.9 M	At 70° for 3 hr	5%	0.6	Amine
	Isobutyl alcohol, 0.14 M			<1%	—	—
	Hexadecyl mercaptan, 0.1 M	8.8 M	At 60° , 3 hr	52%	1.1	—
$SOCl_2$, 0.1 M	Solvent Petroleum ether, 2.4% v/v	8.9 M	At 70° , 4 hr	18%	1.5	Chlorine
$SOCl_2$, 0.09 M	Pet. ether 20% v/v	7.5 M	"	16%	0.9	"
$SOCl_2$, 0.035 M	Pet. ether 66% v/v	3.1 M	"	17%	0.2	"